

DEVELOPMENT OF PALANGKA RAYA CITY PARK IN ACCORDANCE WITH ENVIRONMENTAL CHARACTERISTICS AND REGULATIONS

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ABSTRACT

This paper discusses the development of the Palangka Raya city park with new reviews following the characteristics of the area. Some existing studies are sufficient for the development of urban green open spaces, but none have focused on suitable plant species according to the environment and regulations. For this reason, this discussion describes important basics for achieving it. The function of public and private green open spaces has main ecological functions, and additional architectural, social and economic functions. Urban areas with these four main functions can be combined according to the needs, interests and sustainability of the city.

Keywords: city park, green open space, environment, regulations

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1. INTRODUCTION

In connection with the arrangement of green open space in urban areas (Regulation of The Minister of Public Work Number: 05 / PRT / M / 2008), cities must meet the minimum area requirements for green space requirements of 30% of the administrative area, 20 m² / population and certain functional needs. The regulation defines green open space (RTH) is an elongated area / lane and or grouped, which is more open use, a place to grow plants either naturally or planted. Green space has the main function of ecological namely the lungs of the city, microclimate regulator, shade, oxygen producers, rain water absorbers, providers of animal habitats, absorbers of air, water and soil media pollutants and windbreaks (Fernando et al., 2018; Kotta et al., 2018; Ludang, 2019).

The strategy of developing Palangka Raya city park with suitable vegetation types from Sebangau National Park with the following analysis (Hakim and Utomo, 2004): 2 median road parks, 2 shoulder road parks, 2 city parks and 2 roundabout parks. Utilization of suitable

vegetation types from Sebangau National Park will support efforts to fulfill the additional functions of green space and biological conservation. The hope is that green space that has forest plants, like mangoosten plants and rambutan forest, as well as having a high absorption ability of carbon dioxide (Ludang et al., 2018). More than that, the plants can be a tourist attraction, educational facilities, research and help maintain the germplasm of the forests of Central Kalimantan. Therefore, this paper examines the strategy of developing Palangka Raya city park with selected types of plants suitable for the Sebangau National Park.

2. REVIEW EXISTING STUDIES

Some studies related to references about green open space in Indonesia, including the writings of Maldini et al. (2019). This study is about the Suitability Analysis of the Green Open Space of Magelang City Using Geographic Information Systems. It was stated that based on high-resolution image processing, the area of green open space in Magelang was 30.91% which consisted of public open green space of 11.99% and private green open space of 18.93%. The availability of green space for the classification of Magelang City parks as a whole meets the minimum area of park units in each district. The suitability of green open space in Magelang City between the results of digitization with green open space in the appropriate spatial plan is 1,778,888.45 m² and not suitable is 4,097,082.44 m².

Research by Sriui et al (2019) with the title Analysis of Availability and Needs and Strategies for Developing Parks as Green Open Space in Jambi City a number of park development strategies are needed. The strategy for the availability and development of parks as green open spaces in Jambi City includes: increasing public park areas to fulfill intrinsic and extrinsic functions that can be utilized by the wider community and together, increasing awareness of the importance of parks, and the use and use of appropriate technology and the need to innovate, increase participation and collaboration with the private sector / other business entities in planning and implementation, and to socialize the availability of park functions for life and the environment, broaden and study the uneven distribution of park arrangements.

According to Rosawatiningsih (2018) on the Policy of Green Open Space Management (RTH) of Taman Flora Surabaya, that the high interest of the community, especially urban communities to conduct tour activities, makes the city government have to innovate by developing Green Open Space (RTH) as a place that has complex functions. This study describes what activities people do when they visit Taman Flora so as to produce a social structure that is interconnected and inseparable. The results of the study mentioned that the function of Flora Park is very complex including the educational function, health function, economic function and interaction function. All of these functions can work because visitors, government, private parties, traders, managers and the community carry out the roles carried according to their status. Each structure that carries out its duties properly will also give a good influence on the condition of Taman Flora Surabaya.

Research by Pradipta et al (2018) on the Analysis of Suitability of Green Open Spaces and Parks in Sukoharjo District Using Geographic Information Systems that based on high resolution image processing, the area of green space in Sukoharjo Regency is 9,319,144,411 m² or around 1.89% of the total area of Sukoharjo Regency which is equal to 492,130,650 m².

According to Suciyani (2018) regarding "Analysis of Potential Utilization of Green Open Space (RTH) of Campus in Bandung State Polytechnic" is motivated by a problem regarding green space that has not been used optimally in accordance with its function. The purpose of this study is to analyze the potential utilization of RTH Polban campus which can still be

developed so as to create a sustainable campus environment. The method in this study uses a qualitative approach to the type of applied research (applied research), in addition to data collection techniques using triangulation (observation, interviews, and documentation studies) and analysis techniques in this study are descriptive. Based on the results of the analysis, it is known that the existing conditions of RTH Polban campus have not been used optimally according to the function of RTH due to the lack of facilities that can support activities in the form of socio-cultural, economic, and aesthetic functions.

The research of Pangesti and Dwirani (2018) on the Analysis of the Suitability of Green Open Space in Serang City with the results of the study shows that the area of Green City of Serang is still not sufficient in the provisions of the Law. The total area of green open space in 2016 was 7361.7 ha or around 27.6% of the Serang City Government's area of 2,518.9 ha filled with public open green space while the rest, 4,842.2 ha, was filled by private green open space. Only green open space in two sub-districts fulfilled Permendagri Number 1 of 2007 and PU Permen Number 05 / PRT / M / 2008 namely Kasemen and Cipocok Jaya sub-districts.

Research by Mulyati and Mustika (2019) with the title Study of Oxygen Demand for Green Open Space of the Stork Campus of Musi Charitas Catholic University in Palembang, it is known that the total oxygen demand needed by the residents of the UKMC campus of Bangau, and vehicles is 10,006.12 kg / day. The need for green space on the UKMC campus is still less than 25.99% of the expected 30%. Efforts should be made to meet oxygen consumption by adding plants that can absorb more carbon dioxide such as the tongue-in-law (*Sansevieria*), bamboo palm (*Chamaedorea seifrizii*), yellow palm (*Chrysalidocarpus*), ornamental rubber (*Ficus robusta*) which can be planted in pots and made in the vertical garden.

Furthermore Miharja et al (2018) on Analysis of Green Open Space Needs as an Absorbent of Carbon Gas Emissions in the City and Buffer Area of Malang City with quantitative methods used to determine the extent and ability of the existing green space to absorb CO₂ and the amount of CO₂ released. The total emissions of CO₂ gas produced amounted to 535,429 tons / year. The need for green space is based on the total emissions of 9,139 ha with the current available green space area of 13.09 ha so that it takes 9,126 ha of additional land to balance the need for green space.

Furthermore Haryanto et al (2015) about Analysis of Forest Stand Vegetation in Gunung Sari City Forest Area, Singkawang City obtained research results in the Gunung Sari City Forest area with an area of 150 ha found 53 species of vegetation belonging to 26 families. Of the 53 types of vegetation there are among them having economic value and high potential, such as aloes (*Aquilaria malaccensis*), durian (*Durio zibethinus*), and rubber (*Hevea brasiliensis*). Species diversity from tree to seedling levels in the area has moderate species diversity and tree density conditions at each growth level are still good.

Research by Rochim and Syahbana (2013) on the Determination of Vegetation Function and Suitability in Public Parks as Green Open Space (RTH) in Pekalongan City (Case Study: Monument Park 45 in Pekalongan City), the stages carried out in this study were to analyze the physical condition of the park, analysis of park functions, analysis of park vegetation and analysis of determining the function and suitability of park vegetation. The method used in this study is to conduct field observations, structured interviews and document review. The information obtained from the results of the study is that in general the selection of vegetation to fill the park does not have certain criteria, this is because the location is a location with flood-free land, so that the selection of vegetation was not carried out in detail.

Based on several previous studies that have focused on analyzing the suitability of green open space based on area, population, oxygen demand, and water availability, the novelty in

this study is that the development strategy of Palangka Raya city park has not been carried out by verification of suitable vegetation from Sebangau National Park. to the application of parks in the city of Palangka Raya through the characteristics of these plants.

3. GREEN OPEN SPACE DEVELOPMENT

3.1. Physical Green Open Space

Space includes land space, sea space, and air space, including space in the earth as a unitary region, human place and other living creatures, carrying out activities, and maintaining their survival (Law No.26, 2007 concerning Spatial Planning article 1 paragraph 1).

Common spaces that are part of the environment also have a pattern. A public space is a place or space formed because of the need for a place to meet or communicate with each other. With the existence of joint human activities, it is likely that various activities will occur in the public space. Thus it can also be said that this general space is basically a container that can accommodate certain activities / activities of humans, both individually or in groups (Hakim and Utomo, 2004).

Open space is spaces within the city or wider region both in the form of area / area as well as in the form of elongated areas / paths in which the use is more open in nature without building. Open space consists of green open space and non-green open space (Minister Regulation Number 5 / PRT / M / 2008 Chapter I No. 17).

Urban green open space (RTHKP) is part of an urban open space filled with plants and plants to support ecological, social, cultural, economic and aesthetic benefits (Regulation of the Minister of Home Affairs Number 1 of 2007 in chapter 1 article 1 paragraph 2).

Green open space (RTH) is an elongated area / path and / or group, the use of which is more open, a place to grow plants, both those that grow naturally and are intentionally planted. Non-green open space, is open space in urban areas that are not included in the green space category, in the form of hardened land or in the form of water bodies (Ministerial Regulation Number 5 / PRT / M / 2008 Chapter I No. 18).

Green open space (RTH) consists of 1) private green open space, is RTH belonging to a particular institution or individual whose utilization is for a limited circle, among others in the form of gardens or yard houses / buildings owned by the public / private planted with plants; 2) public green open space, is green space that is owned and managed by the city / regency regional government that is used for the benefit of the community in general. The purpose of organizing green open space (RTH) is to maintain the availability of land as a water catchment area; creating urban planological aspects through a balance between the natural environment and the built environment that is useful for the benefit of the community; and increasing the harmony of the urban environment as a means of safeguarding a safe, comfortable, fresh, beautiful and clean urban environment (Ministerial Regulation Number 5 / PRT / M / 2008).

Based on Minister Regulation No. 5 of 2008 there are two functions of green open space in urban areas, namely:

1. The main (intrinsic) function, which is the ecological function: guarantees the provision of green space to be part of the air circulation system (city lungs); micro climate regulator so that the natural air and water circulation system can run smoothly; as a shelter; oxygen producers; rain water absorber; provider of animal habitat; absorbent of air, water and soil media pollutants, as well as; windbreak.
2. Additional (extrinsic) functions, namely: social and cultural functions: describe local cultural expressions; is a communication media for city residents; Recreation areas; place and

object of education, research and training in studying nature; economic function: the source of products that can be sold, such as flowers, fruits, leaves, vegetables; can be part of the business of agriculture, plantation, forestry and others; and aesthetic functions: increasing comfort, beautifying the city environment from the micro scale: home page, residential and macro environment: the overall urban landscape; stimulating the creativity and productivity of city residents; forming factors architectural beauty; create a harmonious and balanced atmosphere between the built and not awakened areas.

The benefits and functions of the availability of green open space is very important for the survival of a city. The functions of this green space are: (1) Maintaining the availability of land as a water catchment area in the environment; (2) Creating a planological aspect of the environment through a balance between the natural environment and the built environment that is useful for the benefit of the community; (3) Increase the aesthetic value of the area; (4) Adding recreation facilities and interactions in the area for the benefit of the community.

Based on the Directorate General of Spatial Planning Guidelines of the Department of Public Works in 2007, it states that the function of green open space is as follows: conservation areas for hydrological preservation; runaway water control areas by providing retention ponds; area of biodiversity development; the area of creating a micro-climate and reducing pollutants in urban areas; recreational areas and community sports; public burial place; limiting urban development in unexpected directions; securing natural, artificial and historical resources; provision of private green open space, through density restrictions and utilization criteria; disaster mitigation / evacuation area; and signage space in accordance with statutory regulations and does not interfere with the main functions of the green space.

The function of green open space, both public open green space and private green open space, has the main (intrinsic) function, namely ecological functions, and additional (extrinsic) functions, namely architectural, social, and economic functions. An urban area with these four main functions can be combined according to the needs, interests and sustainability of the city. Green space functions ecologically that guarantees the sustainability of an urban area physically, it must be a form of green space that is located, sized and shaped in a certain area of the city, such as green space for the protection of human life support resources and to build a network of wildlife habitat. Green space for other functions (social, economic, architectural) is green space supporting and adding value to the city's environmental and cultural quality, so that it can be located and shaped according to its needs and interests, such as for beauty, recreation, and supporting urban architecture.

Based on the Minister of Public Works Regulation Number 5 / PRT / M / 2008 concerning guidelines for the provision and utilization of open space in urban areas is divided into 3, namely:

1. Provision of green space based on area.

The proportion in urban areas is 30% which consists of 20% public green open space and 10% private green open space.

2. Provision of green open space based on population

3. Provision of green space with special functions.

The provision of green space with this special function, must refer to local regulations because it will greatly affect the order of urban planning, for example, the cemetery must be provided at least 1.2 m² for residents with locations spread throughout the city area.

3.2. Vegetation Suitability Analysis

Vegetation suitability analysis is appropriate; harmony (about opinions, understandings, tones, color combinations, and as); suitability of the choice of vegetation according to the type

of garden. Means the suitability of vegetation is a description of the level of suitability of vegetation types for a particular use, for example parks (Rochim and Syahbana, 2013).

Vegetation as referred to in paragraph (1) is adapted to the shape and nature as well as its purpose, namely: a. botanical, is a mixture of small, medium size, large size trees, half-tree shrubs, shrubs, shrubs and ground / surface cover crops; b. architectural, is the heterogeneity of the shape of the rounded, spreading, triangular, column shape, pole shape, umbrella and stretching, and has exotic values from the angle of the flower color, leaf color, fruit, stem texture, branching structure; and c. plants that are developed do not harm humans and pay attention to values (Regulation of the Minister of Home Affairs Number 1 of 2007).

Kurniawan and Alfian (2010) stated that plants have aesthetic value and also function to increase environmental quality. The function of plants as visual control, physical barriers, climate control, erosion control, wild habitat and aesthetic values. Aesthetic value is obtained from a combination of colors (leaves, stems, flowers), the physical shape of the plant (stems, branches, crowns), plant texture, and plant composition.

Furthermore Hakim and Utomo (2004) plant characteristics can be seen from the shape of the trunk and branching, canopy shape, leaf mass, flower mass, color, texture, accentuation, height scale and solitude. Arrangement of plants must be adjusted to the objectives of the plan without forgetting the function of the selected plant. In this laying must also consider the balance in design (unity). So, in landscape plant planning, the choice of plant type is an important factor.

Hakim and Utomo (2004) stated that the selection of plant species in a landscape design is an art and science. Art because it involves the composition of design elements such as color, shape, texture, and design quality that changes because it is greatly influenced by climate, age, and natural factors. Science is concerned with laying techniques, planting techniques and growth. The choice of plant type depends on: the function of the plant, according to the design goals; and placement of plants, according to the function of plants.

The physical characteristics of plants can be seen from the shape of the stem and branching, the shape of the crown, leaf mass, flower mass, color, texture, accentuation, scale of height and solitude. General requirements for plants to be planted in urban areas include plants that are liked and not harmful to city residents, are able to grow in marginal environments (infertile soil, polluted air and water), resistant to vandalism, deep roots and not easily uprooted, not deciduous, fast growing, ornamental and architectural value, can produce O₂ and improve the quality of the city environment, priority using endemic or local vegetation and biodiversity. The selection of vegetation for public parks must pay attention to the character and the suitability criteria so that it is expected to be able to trigger a clean and shady city atmosphere. In addition, the selection of vegetation should be adjusted to suitability criteria that include the initial function of public parks, aesthetics, ecosystems, soil type, climatology of the area, maintenance (maintenance) as well as the biology of the plants filling the park (Rochim and Syahbana, 2013).

4. CONCLUSION

Green open space is developed based on basic considerations in the form of applicable laws and regulations. It must also comprehensively consider ecological aspects, urban architecture, and community acceptance. This issue needs special attention in future research.

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